

TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING HEALTHY LIFESTYLE SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18456012>

Abstract. *The article examines the importance and effectiveness of pedagogical technologies in shaping a healthy lifestyle among students majoring in physical education. In the modern educational process, the development of a healthy lifestyle not only strengthens students' health but also contributes to increasing their intellectual and social activity.*

Keywords: *physical education, healthy lifestyle, pedagogical technology, student, health, anthropometry.*

Introduction

In the modern information society, it is necessary to provide many conditions for maintaining people's health and quality of life, among which general and medical literacy are of great importance. By creating pedagogical conditions for students to understand the importance of health in the context of modern global problems and forming a healthy lifestyle in them, we can also achieve an increase in health and medical culture among the population. Innovative approaches to developing healthy lifestyle skills in future physical culture specialists include the use of health protection and information and communication technologies, game and competition methodologies, level differentiation, as well as interdisciplinary integration and project-oriented training. This serves to train competitive specialists who are able to form a healthy lifestyle in themselves and others using modern methods and taking into account individual needs. It is worth noting that the more educated a person is, the more responsibly he approaches his health. The foundations of valeological knowledge should be formed in the family, and systematized and improved in educational institutions of all levels. Based on this, the role of educators in shaping the health of the future generation is of particular importance.

Modern science defines human health as consisting of the following components: functional-structural – the ability of all systems and organs of the body to function normally, their mutual harmony; physico-chemical – aspects of body structure, metabolism, immunity and biological processes that determine the level of health; psycho-emotional – psychological stability, emotional state and stress tolerance; spiritual – the moral, cultural and social health of a person, harmony with life values. Thus, health is a complex and multifaceted concept that combines the physical, mental and spiritual aspects of a person.

The international organization UNESCO divides the concept of health into three components: physical health (somatic), mental health and spiritual health. It can be seen from this that health is a sufficiently deep and multifaceted concept that, with its complexity, not only analyzes different levels of the human structure, but also expresses its individual uniqueness. By creating pedagogical conditions for students to understand the importance of health in the context of modern global problems and to form a healthy lifestyle in them, we can also achieve an increase in health and medical culture among the population. Innovative approaches to the development of

healthy lifestyle skills in future physical education specialists include the use of health protection and information and communication technologies, game and competition methodologies, level differentiation, as well as interdisciplinary integration and project-oriented teaching. This serves to train competitive specialists who, using modern methods and taking into account individual needs, are able to form a healthy lifestyle in themselves and others. It is worth noting that the more educated a person is, the more responsibly he approaches his health.

The foundations of valeological knowledge should be formed from the family, and systematized and improved in the conditions of educational institutions of all levels. Based on this, the role of educators in shaping the health of the future generation is of particular importance. Although the main task of higher educational institutions is to form the competence of maintaining a healthy lifestyle in future physical education teachers, the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms of this process have not been sufficiently developed. Solving this problem requires the development of theoretical foundations for the formation of the competence of maintaining a healthy lifestyle, that is, medical and scientific literacy, in students of the physical education department of pedagogical universities, the creation of its model, and the identification of conditions ensuring its effective implementation.

In the conditions of the constantly changing economic situation in modern society, the issue of strengthening and preserving the health of students and youth traditionally remains one of the most important issues and requires a new approach to its solution. It is necessary to develop effective preventive measures, form a stable motivation in students for a healthy lifestyle, and develop the need for physical and psychological self-improvement. The future physical education teacher must be able to effectively use modern pedagogical technologies, innovative methods and health-improving programs in his work. This will have a positive effect not only on the physical development of students, but also on their spiritual and mental state, and on their willpower. Also, such a teacher, by his personal example, will show the importance of a healthy lifestyle, instill in students a sense of responsibility for their own health and the desire for a healthy life. The essence and structure of the concept of "Healthy lifestyle - competence" of a future specialist is that healthy lifestyle - competence is not just having knowledge about health, but the ability of a future physical culture specialist to maintain his own health, design a healthy lifestyle and teach these skills to others at a professional level.

The relevance of forming healthy lifestyle skills in future specialists is not only to achieve sports results, but also to improve the culture of health in society and create a mechanism for raising a mentally and physically healthy generation. Physical culture and sports, as an integral part of socio-economic development, have many directions and goals. The lifestyle of any person covers many aspects. These two concepts affect the process of self-awareness and self-improvement, the formation of will. Recently, the influence of physical culture and sports on the development of the student's personality has been steadily increasing. A healthy lifestyle is a controlled process that should take into account the interests, motivations, level of physical fitness of students and the capabilities of the higher educational institution.

Properly organized active physical culture and sports promotion plays a major role in successfully solving these issues. This includes increasing the level of knowledge of students in the field of physical education, educating the need to adopt a healthy lifestyle, using physical culture tools in the work and leisure regime, activating extracurricular forms of physical education and health work among students, involving all members of the team in participation in mass health, physical education and sports events, It is extremely necessary to increase the effectiveness of

physical education classes and physical education and health-improving activities, and to improve mass physical education work among students.

In the modern higher education system, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students is an important pedagogical task. This process is effectively carried out not only through physical education classes, but also through the use of interactive, innovative pedagogical technologies. Physical culture also has such a function that it is the transfer of experience in creating modern technologies and using means of regulating the psychophysical state of people; this forms the basis for the development of health technologies. If physical culture is a means of increasing labor productivity and achieving high results in professional activity, then professional activity, in turn, provides appropriate conditions (material and spiritual) for the development of physical culture. A healthy lifestyle is an indicator of how a person uses the living conditions in the environment for his health. Components (components) of a healthy lifestyle: physical activity, exercise, rational nutrition, adherence to the daily routine, personal hygiene, rejection of harmful habits. An important component of a healthy lifestyle of young people is playing sports. A specialist's healthy lifestyle competence is manifested through the following three interrelated components:

1. Structural structure of competence

- Cognitive component: Deep theoretical knowledge of human physiology, hygiene, proper nutrition, distribution of physical loads and the consequences of harmful habits.
- Motivational-value component: Recognition of health as the highest vital and professional value, an internal need to constantly work on oneself.
- Active component: The ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, regularly engage in sports, form stress resistance skills and develop health programs.

2. Assessment criteria and indicators The following criteria are used to determine the STT-competence of students: Level of knowledge. Perfection of medical-biological and pedagogical knowledge, understanding of the methodology of a healthy lifestyle. Motivation. The will to be healthy, interest in sports, striving for professional success. Personal example. The student's appearance (anthropometry), freedom from harmful habits, level of physical fitness. Methodical skills. The ability to explain the rules of a healthy lifestyle to others and conduct promotional work. The formation of students' health through pedagogical means depends on the efforts of teachers of all specialties, the entire teaching staff; also, the higher the health culture of all participants in the educational process, the more effective health care activities will be.

However, today the main problem is that a healthy lifestyle is not given priority in society, and the role of health in the educational space is not sufficiently understood. This has aroused great interest in various aspects of physical culture and requires its detailed study. Pedagogical technologies are systematic methods of planning, monitoring and evaluating the educational process, through which student motivation increases, knowledge and skills are strengthened. In the application of pedagogical technology for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students in the direction of physical culture, physical education tools, non-traditional methods and assessment of the physical development of adolescents, as well as interactive classes, play an important role. This process is aimed at developing their physical qualities and requires the application of the scientific foundations of physical culture, modern pedagogical approaches (for example, differentiation, design, interactive games, person-oriented approaches). The following methods are considered effective in the direction of physical culture:

1. Active learning methods - for example, group classes, sports games, innovative trainings encourage students to actively participate.

2. Individual approach - adapting classes to each student's physical condition and abilities.
3. Information and communication technologies - making the process interesting through online lessons, electronic monitoring, and mobile applications that promote a healthy lifestyle.
4. Through the use of pedagogical technologies, students gain skills to improve their health, effectively manage time, and increase social activity.

The formation of healthy lifestyle components was defined as a set of the following:

- A valuable attitude towards health and a healthy lifestyle;
- The degree of students' mastery of methods and means of maintaining and strengthening personal health.
- The ability to set the goals of their own personal healthy lifestyle program. The ability to set the goals of their own personal healthy lifestyle program.
 1. Purposefulness. Setting clear (SMART) health goals.
 2. Consistency. Systematic, not one-time, training and healthy habits.
 3. Scientificity. Relying on medical and physical education rules when creating a program.
 4. Effectiveness. Recording achievements (for example, reducing shortness of breath).

The ability to set the goals of a personal healthy lifestyle program is the highest stage of a student's transition from passive maintenance of their health to active and strategic management of it. Such an approach, based on the principles of purposefulness, consistency, scientificity and effectiveness, establishes valeological competence, which allows a person to model and optimize his physical and mental capabilities throughout his life. The formation of a healthy lifestyle for students in the direction of physical culture is effectively carried out using pedagogical technologies. This not only improves their physical health, but also contributes to their intellectual and social development. Therefore, the widespread use of pedagogical technologies in higher educational institutions is recommended. Based on research and analysis, the following final conclusions were drawn: Specialist - social role model: Future specialists must be formed as "health ambassadors" who not only teach sports skills, but also set a personal example for society in terms of physical activity, proper nutrition and abstinence from harmful habits. Comprehensive and systematic approach: The process of forming STT should combine theory, practice and modern pedagogical technologies (for example, asymmetric gymnastics, SMART goals). This process should be seen as a single mechanism that ensures both the physical and intellectual-spiritual development of the student.

Controlled and motivational process: The formation of STT in higher education institutions is a clearly controlled process that takes into account the student's personal interests and motivation. This process turns the student from a passive participant into an active subject who projects his own health. Promotion and publicity: The use of creative and effective promotional methods and the involvement of the entire academic community in extracurricular sports events are of great importance in promoting the culture of STT.

The use of technologies for the formation of a healthy lifestyle allows the development of such basic characteristics of the student's personality as a tendency to cognition and self-awareness, high-level needs and value relationships. In addition, these technologies serve to reassess the meaning of their life activities, to achieve success, to be recognized, to realize their abilities, including the need to change their lifestyle. Diagnostics, in turn, allows you to increase motivation for physical education classes and forms a healthy lifestyle in students. In conclusion,

the formation of healthy lifestyle competencies in future physical education specialists is of paramount importance.

After all, they should be role models and promoters of a healthy lifestyle that affects the health of society and the formation of a comprehensively developed personality through physical activity, proper nutrition, giving up bad habits and stress management. This requires a comprehensive approach to education, combining theory, practice and personal example. The formation of healthy lifestyle competencies in future physical culture specialists is not just an educational task, but a strategic necessity aimed at preserving the gene pool of society. By forming healthy lifestyle skills, we will not only achieve sporting achievements, but also create a system for educating a strong-willed and comprehensively developed generation that feels responsible for its own health.

Conclusion

Based on the holistic concept of health, teaching a healthy lifestyle includes not only physical self-improvement, mastering methods of maintaining and strengthening health, but also the formation of the motivational and spiritual sphere of health: a value-based approach to health, the need for self-awareness and improvement. The formation of healthy lifestyle competencies in future physical culture specialists is not just an educational task, but a strategic necessity aimed at preserving the gene pool of society. By forming healthy lifestyle skills, we will not only achieve sporting achievements, but also create a system for raising a strong-willed and comprehensively developed generation that feels responsible for its own health.

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